

$e/T \ll 1$ Approximation of Tsallis $\ln_q = \{ (e/T)^q - 1 \} / (1-q)$

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In a previous note (1), we argued that one may obtain the Tsallis unnormalized distribution $\exp_q = \{ 1 - (1-q)e/T \}^{1/(1-q)}$ by seeking a function which yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann unnormalized distribution $\exp(-e/T)$ for $e/T \ll 1$, but for higher e/T values, weights e/T by q . In such a scenario, the low e/T yields $\exp(-e/T)$ for any q value. The fact that $q=1$ yields $\exp(-e/T)$ for all e/T shows the effect of the weight q as the full Maxwell-Boltzmann case includes all e/T values.

Here we try to derive the Tsallis $\ln_q = \{ x^q - 1 \} / (1-q)$ by using the e/T approximation. In particular we argue that $\ln_q(\exp_q(e/T)) = -e/T$ for $e/T \ll 1$ as this is the MB case and that $\exp_q(e/T) = \exp(-e/T) = 1 - e/T$ for the $e/T \ll 1$ case. We do not assume a priori that \ln_q is associated with a single parameter q , but consider a power series expansion which may include many powers and then show that there is only one in the $e/T \ll 1$ case. Thus, using the $e/T \ll 1$ case, we argue that one may obtain the general \ln_q form. We argue that this form is important because it appears in the Tsallis entropy expression: $\sum_i p_i^q \ln_q(p_i)$.

Tsallis \exp_q Function and $e/T \ll 1$

In (1) we suggested a physical picture in which the Maxwell-Boltzmann scenario fully applies for $(e_i - e_{ave})/T \ll 1$. In other words, the two body elastic scattering probability:

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3) f(e_4) \quad ((1a)) \text{ for } e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1b))$$

is considered to be completely true only for this condition. When $(e_i - e_{ave})/T$ is no longer small, we suggest that other factors may also determine whether a collision occurs and not simply the presence of the particle. Speed, for example, could be one of these factors because a fast particle has a greater chance of encountering other particles in a delta time.

We suggested that the Tsallis approach is to weight $(e_i - e_{ave})/T$ by a factor q . If $q=1$, there is no weight and so one should obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann scenario. One should, however, also obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann result for any q for $(e_i - e_{ave})/T$ if $(e_i - e_{ave})/T \ll 1$, as we argued in (1). This restricts the form of the distribution in question.

Here, we try to apply the $(e_i - e_{ave})/T \ll 1$ reasoning to \ln_q such that:

$$\ln_q(\exp_q(e/T)) = -e/T \quad ((2))$$

In other words, \ln_q and \exp_q are considered to be inverse functions for any q .

\ln_q Function and $e/T \ll 1$

Going forward, we use e/T instead of $(e_i - e_{ave})/T$. We note first that in the $e/T \ll 1$ case:

$$\ln_q(1 - e/T) = -e/T \quad ((3))$$

Here $1-e/T$ is the approximation of $\exp(-e/T)$ for $e/T \ll 1$. From (1), the unnormalized Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution should apply to $\exp q$ for $e/T \ll 1$.

At this point, $\ln q$ is simply an unknown function. We do not consider q to represent a single parameter.

As a first step, we suggest a power law expansion of $\ln q$. We consider positive integers as powers for simplicity. Then:

$$(1-e/T)^{\text{power } q} \approx 1 - qe/T \quad ((4)) \quad \text{because } e/T \ll 1$$

One may ask whether there may be many such q powers, e.g. q_1, q_2, q_3 etc

Given that ((3)) must be satisfied, one requires bringing in the number -1 to cancel the 1 in ((4)). If there are many powers, q_1, q_2 etc, one requires:

$$(1-q_1e/T)^{1/a_1} + (1-q_2e/T)^{1/a_2} + \dots - 1 = -e/T \quad ((5)) \quad \text{or:} \quad \sum \text{over } i \ 1/a_i = 1 \quad ((6a))$$

$$\text{and } \sum \text{over } i \ q_i/a_i = 1 \quad ((6b))$$

If q_i are positive integers which are not equal, one cannot have ((6a)) and ((6b)) satisfied. This suggests that there should only be one power q_1 and perhaps explains why Tsallis entropy is based on only one power.

If there is only one power, then:

$$\{(1-e/T)^{\text{power } q}\}^{-1} = 1 - qe/T^{-1} = -q e/T \quad \text{so one should divide by } q \text{ to eliminate}$$

q dependence which is supposed to disappear for $e/T \ll 1$ according to our arguments.

One may next map q to $1-q$ to obtain:

$$\{(1-e/T)^{\text{power } 1-q} - 1\} / (1-q) \quad ((7))$$

If one finally replaces $1-e/T$ with its general value for all e/T , one has $\exp q(e/T)$ in place of $1-e/T$. Treating $\exp q$ as a variable x , one has: $\{x^{\text{power } 1-q} - 1\} / (1-q)$ which yields $\ln(x)$ for $q \rightarrow 1$.

Thus, we suggest that small e/T considerations lead to the form of $\ln q$ in the Tsallis case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggested in (1) that one may find the Tsallis distribution by suggesting that for $(e_i - e_{ave})/T \ll 1$ one has $\exp(-e/T)$ as the distribution (i.e. the unnormalized Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.) We then suggested that one may consider changes as e/T is no longer small being quantified by qe/T . (Here we replace $(e_i - e_{ave})/T$ by e/T .) The key point is

that regardless of the value of q , one obtains $\exp(-e/T)$ for $e/T \ll 1$. In (1), we showed that this leads to $\{1 - (1-q)e/T\}^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)}$ as a possible solution.

In this note, we consider trying to find \ln_q , the inverse function of \exp_q , using e/T considerations. We begin with $\ln_q(\exp_q(e/T)) = -e/T$ and suggest a power series for \ln_q using positive integers as a first attempt. We do not consider \ln_q being restricted to one q power, but show that this must be the case. As a result, we obtain the single q \ln_q Tsallis logarithm. This logarithm is important, we argue, because Tsallis entropy is: $\sum \text{over } i \text{ } p_i^{\text{power } q} \ln_q(f_i)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Obtaining the Tsallis Distribution from $e/T \ll 1$ and $e/T \gg 1$ Considerations? (preprint, zenodo, 2025)